

Modulating Pain Perception: Music Therapy as a Dual-Pathway Intervention for Pain Management

Throughout history, music has been a powerful tool for fostering a sense of togetherness, shaping individual identities, and cultivating unique cultural expressions (“The Transformative Power of Music”). Additionally, some research suggests that music has an impact on pain perception. Specifically, pain is typically triggered by nociceptors, which send signals through peripheral axons to the dorsal horn of the spinal cord and then onto the thalamus (Timmerman et al.). However, endorphins and memory distractions reduce nociceptor stimulation, thereby alleviating pain (Timmerman et al.).

Physical pain can be categorized into two types: acute and chronic. Acute pain takes place suddenly and produces heightened stimulation to the nociceptors. Acute pain is described as a short, intense sensation that is often characterized as a piercing or sharp sensation. However, chronic pain persists for more extended periods, usually months or years. However, unlike acute pain, chronic pain is often less intense than acute pain.

It is essential to consider that pain does not always have physical origins but can also have psychological origins. According to Dakota Family Services, a renowned center for mental health services, pain can originate from anywhere in the body. However, because the body is not able to differentiate between physical and psychological pain, psychological pain is often manifested as physical pain in the abdomen (“The Connection Between Emotional and Physical Pain”).

Current pain management is often used through psychological, pharmacological, and surgical means. However, these pain management methods have their limitations as of 2024.

Nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are “a pharmacological drug used for the management of arthritis and acute and chronic pain of many etiologies, including cancer-related pain. These drugs are indicated for use as single agents in mild to moderate pain and in combination with opioid analgesics or adjuvant analgesic drugs in severe pain” (Payne 14).

However, NSAIDs can have a severe risk of blood toxicity (hematologic toxicity) when used for acute pain, and for chronic pain, NSAIDs can have a severe risk of nephrotoxicity. Additionally, people who use NSAIDs for diseases such as HIV/AIDS are more susceptible to this toxicity. Because of HIV/AIDS’s nature to significantly weaken the immune system, the adverse effects of NSAIDs, such as nephrotoxicity, are at increased risk (Payne 16). Thus, current pain management methods are effective; however, these techniques still have several limitations and are imperfect.

One promising alternative that shows promise in dealing with both the physical and psychological aspects of pain is the practice of music therapy. But how does music therapy work to deal with pain? When our brains first recognize music, they release dopamine, a neurotransmitter that produces feelings of pleasure and satisfaction. Music is incredibly effective at releasing dopamine (Member). Thus, the brain can identify the most pleasurable peaks of the music, which releases an early onset of dopamine.

Dopamine is a neurotransmitter that influences your mood and is primarily associated with the feeling of pleasure. This quality enables dopamine to reduce the intensity of pain signals, thereby increasing pain tolerance. This process, known as hypoalgesia, is crucial for alleviating pain in everyday scenarios such as taking aspirin, massaging a bruised knee, or undergoing anesthesia (“Neuroscience News”).

Additionally, music evokes robust emotional responses that can help alleviate stress and negative emotions associated with past traumatic experiences, leading to healing and recovery. The University of Kansas Health System states that when we express our feelings, “we loosen the emotion's grip over our well-being. Expressing our emotions brings about a lot more benefits,” such as reducing anxiety and depression, as well as facilitating easier decision-making, and problem-solving (“Why Is Emotional Expression Important?”). However, “when we fail to express our emotions, our brain can often go into the fight-or-flight state. This is a physical reaction to stress that sets off a chain of events throughout the body. It increases our heart rate, slows digestive functions, and makes us feel anxious or depressed” (“Why Is Emotional Expression Important?”).

Research indicates that music activates several parts of our brain, including the limbic system (Beentjes). The limbic system is involved in motivation, emotion, learning, and memory. Stimulating this area of the brain with music can help stabilize mood, reduce anxiety, and alleviate stress, and, therefore, improve one’s mental health and well-being (“Releasing Stress Through the Power of Music”).

Moreover, the therapeutic capabilities of music and its healing qualities have been well established. Music therapy has been able to help individuals with several problems, such as pain, stress, and several mental health conditions. It has been demonstrated that a medley of rhythm, patterns, harmonies, and melodies has a profound impact on the brain, leading to relaxation, an improved mood, and a more stable state of mental health (“The Transformative Power of Music”).

Fundamentally, music therapy is viable because the intertwined connection between dopamine, music, and emotional expression demonstrates the complex ways our bodies work to regulate and alleviate physical and psychological pain, thereby improving one’s well-being.

For thousands of years, music has been used as a form of pain management and healing. Greek physicians used instruments such as the flute in their healing practices. The Greeks believed that the vibrations from the instruments had several positive effects on their patients and their well-being. They thought that the vibrations helped aid digestion, alleviate mental health issues, and induce sleep (Meymandi). Aristotle, a prominent philosopher in his time, wrote about the capabilities of music in his world-renowned book, *De Anima* (Meymandi). According to Aristotle, a flute can create intense emotions and the ability to cleanse one’s soul. This practice of using instruments demonstrates the recognition of music and its properties in society for their positive effects on medicine.

Similarly, the Ancient Egyptians are believed to have used spoken spells, such as chants, to heal the sick. This method reflects the Ancient Egyptians’ belief in spirits and how they were

embedded in their culture and way of thinking (“Ancient Egyptian Medicine”). Therefore, this belief is displayed in the Egyptians’ use of a form of music therapy regarding medicine and physiology.

Since then, music has evolved over the years, beginning in the nineteenth century when it was officially introduced as a therapeutic method. During this time, an observable basis was formed around its introduction into medicine. In 1914, it was recognized that there was a notable amount of benefits pre-operation regarding anxiety levels in patients who were exposed to music (“American Music Therapy Association”). During this time, the benefits of music therapy were emphasized when this method was implemented for soldiers suffering from the effects of World War II; this development cemented music therapy’s place in physical and psychological treatments (“American Music Therapy Association”).

Eventually, in 1998, the National Association for Music Therapy (NAMT) and the American Association for Music Therapy (AAMT) merged into one larger association —the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA) (“American Music Therapy Association”). The American Music Therapy Association serves as a hub for advocating music therapy and providing educational resources for professionals (“American Music Therapy Association”). Alongside the AMTA, the Certification Board for Music Therapists (CBMT) was established to ensure high standards of credibility and competency in the field through a rigorous certification process (“American Music Therapy Association”).

Today, music therapy is increasingly integrated into medical treatments— while being prescribed alongside medications and interventions— for several different illnesses and mental disorders, such as Parkinson’s disease, stroke recovery, dementia, and pain (“Cleveland Clinic Medical”). The increased research towards the benefits of music therapy, new technological advances, and rising interest and support for the therapy’s use encourage a promising future for the field.

In 2018, a study by Rohilla et al. was done on patients in a tertiary care burn unit who were all less than ten years old, conscious, and aware of their surroundings. This study was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of music therapy during burn dressing changes. This experiment was measured in two categories: pain and anxiety. Pain was measured in a standard numerical rating, while anxiety was measured through a State-Trait Anxiety Test: a test that separately measures state and trait anxiety through twenty questions each. The study was conducted as a quasi-experimental, crossover experiment. Patients served as their own control group to reduce variability. To minimize recall bias, patients were called in for their burn dressing changes at least 48 hours apart (Rohilla et al.).

The data from the study show that, assuming H_0 — the hypothesis that music is not practical in reducing anxiety during surgical procedures —is accurate, we are 95% confident that the actual difference between the overall medians of anxiety scores is 2.5, which corresponds to a P-value of 0.001 (Rohilla et al.). Since 0.001 (the probability of the data being an outlier, assuming H_0 is true) is less than 0.05, we reject the original hypothesis: H_0 .

Additionally, the study's data regarding pain shows that, assuming H_0 —the hypothesis that music is not practical in reducing anxiety during surgical procedures —we are 95% confident

that the actual difference between medians on pain scales is -1.5, which corresponds to a P-value of 0.001 (Rohilla et al.). Since 0.001 (the probability of the data being an outlier, assuming H_0 is true) is less than 0.05, we reject the original hypothesis: H_0 .

However, it is worth noting that before the dressing change started, assuming H_0 is accurate, we are 95% confident that the proper comparison between the Trait Anxiety scores with and without music is -1.71 standard deviations away from the mean or has a probability of 0.087 (Rohilla et al.). Since $0.087 > .05$, we fail to reject H_0 and can assume that music therapy is ineffective in lessening Trait Anxiety before, during, and after a dressing change.

In this study, most participants chose religious music, such as the Gayatri mantra and Shabad, as their genre (Rohilla et al.). This begs the question of whether the choice of music matters in reducing pain during a procedure.

In a study by Lu et al., researchers found 28 healthy individuals and subjected them to nociceptive laser stimuli. During the stimulus, either their favorite, most disliked, or no music was played. When music that was liked by the subject was played during the laser stimulus, the areas of the brain that are responsible for interpreting pain, like the right precentral and postcentral gyri; areas of the brain in charge of physical reactions to pain, like the left cerebellum; and areas of the brain which are accountable for the mood disturbances in accordance with pain were less active when compared to the activation of the brain while playing disliked music or no music at all (Lu et al.).

Additionally, a study from the University of Utah found that the effectiveness of pain stimuli decreased as music became increasingly intensified (“Study Assesses Pain”). Scientists found that this was because music utilizes the same sensory pathways as pain and engages a greater amount of cognitive processing and attention. Thus displaying the direct negative correlation between intensified music and a decreased sensation of pain.

These findings further demonstrate the applicability of music therapy as a future adaptive form of complementary medicine. Using personalized music as a distraction to mitigate the effects of pain highlights the vast potential of music therapy in healthcare. Furthermore, these findings open the doors for several other forms of pain therapy. For example, several studies have shown that patients prefer to see dentists who have televisions in their offices compared to those who do not. This is because televisions act as distractors for patients to ease their anxiety before an appointment. These trends and applications perfectly display the reasonability of music therapy as a viable way to put patients at ease and distract them from any pain they might be experiencing.

Additionally, not only is music therapy proving itself to be a viable painkiller, but it is also a way to reduce the recurrence of several diseases and disorders. Music therapy has long been associated with autism since its conception. In an experiment consisting of 165 participants who were all diagnosed with autism-related disorders, aged two to nine years old, researchers wanted to find if music therapy was genuinely effective in helping those with autism; they set up the experiment as a placebo treatment. The results showed a moderate to significant difference between music therapy treatment and the placebo “in outcome areas constituting the core of the

condition, such as social interaction, non-verbal communicative skills, initiating behavior, and social-emotional reciprocity.” Additionally, according to the AMSTAR 2 criteria, the results of the following experiment were assigned a high confidence level, indicating that the results are likely to be accurate (Stegemann et al.).

Several other studies have also found that music therapy is beneficial in reducing medical diseases and disorders, such as epilepsy and seizures. However, the AMSTAR 2 ratings of these experiments were assessed with low confidence (Stegemann et al.). Although this should not discredit the advancements and benefits of music therapy, there are several negatives if it is used incorrectly.

As mentioned above, an experiment examining the effects of liked and disliked music was described, and the results showed that liked music provided more significant benefits than disliked music (Timmerman et al.). Although this is true, specific genres of music that one may like cannot be expected to produce positive results, but rather the opposite.

For example, songs labeled as sad lead to one dwelling on negative emotions and experiences, thus worsening one’s mood. According to researchers, listening to music can provide a sense of community and support; however, during psychological distress, it can lead to intensified, potentially harmful feelings (Botello). This shows how incorrectly using music therapy can be detrimental to someone seeking help for psychological disorders and can do more harm to someone rather than good for their psychological state of being.

In conclusion, because music is directly linked to the deactivation of nociceptors and, in turn, the reduction of pain perception (“Neuroscience News”), music therapy, when used correctly, can be the future of pain therapy and revolutionize the healthcare industry. As mentioned above, several studies demonstrate the effectiveness and applications of music therapy for various patient populations, further supporting the argument for the wider adoption of music therapy as a natural, non-invasive pain management approach.

Music can be utilized in everyday healthcare in the future, alongside various other osteopathic and medicinal procedures, including alternative pain relievers and painkillers. Not only will music therapy be a way to relieve pain during procedures, but it will also be a method to relieve the stress and anxiety one goes through daily by acting as a distractor.

However, this can only occur through the continuance of research regarding the pros and cons of music therapy. If we fail to oblige, the healthcare industry is at risk of losing a crucial revelation regarding the further development. Therefore, we must devote time and effort to combining music, psychology, and medicine to revolutionize the world’s healthcare system. Music has brought a sense of community and belonging for several millennia, and now we can use music to better the lives of the people among us.

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